

Effects of Creative Writing-Oriented Applications on Pre-Service Teachers' Writing Anxiety and Self-Regulation

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Abstract: This study examines the impact of creative writing activities on pre-service teachers' self-regulation competencies and writing anxiety. Writing is a complex process involving cognitive and affective dimensions, and creative writing supports self-expression, self-awareness, and active engagement. However, studies exploring the relationship between creative writing and self-regulation among pre-service teachers are limited. An explanatory sequential mixed-methods design was employed. The quantitative phase used a pre-test–post-test–retention test model, followed by semi-structured interviews in the qualitative phase. The participants consisted of 31 pre-service teachers enrolled in a Turkish Language Teaching program. Over ten weeks, creative writing activities incorporating planning, self-monitoring, self-assessment, and reflection were implemented. Quantitative data were analyzed using repeated-measures ANOVA and correlation analyses, while qualitative data were analyzed through thematic analysis. The findings revealed that creative writing activities significantly increased self-regulation levels and reduced writing anxiety. A moderate negative correlation was found between self-regulation and writing anxiety. Qualitative results indicated improvements in planning, monitoring, and revision, as well as increased confidence and motivation. Overall, the study highlights the effectiveness of integrating creative and self-regulation-oriented approaches into writing education.

Anahtar Sözcükler:

Yaratıcı yazma süreçleri
Yaratıcı yazma süreçleri
Yazmaya yönelik öz-düzenleme
Yazma kaygısı
Öğretmen adayları

Yaratıcı Yazma Odaklı Uygulamaların Öğretmen Adaylarının Yazma Kaygısı ve Yazmaya Yönelik Öz-Düzenleme Yeterlikleri Üzerindeki Etkisi

Özet: Bu çalışma, yaratıcı yazma etkinliklerinin öğretmen adaylarının yazmada öz-düzenleme becerileri ve yazma kaygısı üzerindeki etkisini incelemektedir. Yazma, bilişsel ve duyuşsal boyutları içeren karmaşık bir süreçtir; yaratıcı yazma ise bireylerin kendilerini ifade etmelerini, öz farkındalık geliştirmelerini ve öğrenme sürecine etkin katılım göstermelerini destekler. Buna karşın, öğretmen adayları düzeyinde yaratıcı yazma ile öz-düzenleme arasındaki ilişkiyi ele alan çalışmalar sınırlıdır. Araştırmada açıklayıcı sıralı karma yöntem deseni kullanılmıştır. Nicel aşamada ön test–son test–kalıcılık testi modeli uygulanmış, nitel aşamada yarı yapılandırılmış görüşmeler yapılmıştır. Çalışma grubunu Türkçe öğretmenliği programında öğrenim gören 31 öğretmen adayı oluşturmuştur. On hafta süresince planlama, izleme, öz değerlendirme ve yanıtma süreçlerini içeren yaratıcı yazma etkinlikleri uygulanmıştır. Nicel veriler tekrarlı ölçümler varyans analizi ve korelasyon analizi ile, nitel veriler ise tematik analizle çözümlenmiştir. Bulgular, yaratıcı yazma etkinliklerinin öz-düzenleme düzeylerini anlamlı biçimde artırdığını ve yazma kaygısını azalttığını göstermektedir. Öz-düzenleme ile yazma kaygısı arasında orta düzeyde negatif ilişki belirlenmiştir. Nitel bulgular, planlama, izleme ve gözden geçirme becerilerinde gelişim ile güven ve motivasyonda artış olduğunu ortaya koymaktadır. Sonuçlar, yazma öğretiminde yaratıcı ve öz-düzenleme temelli yaklaşımların etkili olduğunu göstermektedir.

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1. Introduction

Writing is a multi-layered language activity that integrates cognitive, affective, and social processes. It can be conceptualized as a process involving planning, text production, and revision, and as a high-level form of thinking that structures and transforms knowledge. Writing is not only an indicator of linguistic skills but also of metacognitive control (Flower & Hayes, 1981; Galbraith et al., 2007; Kellogg, 2008). In this context, modern writing instruction has shifted towards an understanding that emphasizes process over product; creative thinking, self-awareness, and emotional engagement rather than memorization (Cremin et al., 2012; Graham & Harris, 2018).

Creative writing is an instructional approach that enables individuals to express their feelings, thoughts, and imagination in original forms while also developing thinking and self-expression processes (Beghetto & Kaufman, 2014; Craft, 2001; Oral, 2014). Craft (2001) defines creative writing as “possibility thinking,” emphasizing the individual’s capacity to generate new meanings. International studies have consistently demonstrated the effects of creative writing activities on the quality of written expression, writing self-efficacy, and writing motivation (Cremin et al., 2020; Graham et al., 2015). Galbraith et al. (2007) argue that creative writing is not only an aesthetic activity but also one that promotes cognitive flexibility. Accordingly, creative writing activities can help reduce writing anxiety and enhance learners’ self-confidence and willingness to write by addressing both writing skills and affective dimensions.

The writing process is directly related to self-regulation skills involving cycles of goal setting, planning, self-monitoring, self-assessment, and self-reflection (Boekaerts & Cascallar, 2006; Panadero, 2017; Zimmerman, 2000). Zimmerman and Risemberg (1997) defined self-regulation as the management of one’s cognitive and emotional processes to achieve learning goals; Harris and Graham (2009) emphasized the determining role of this skill in writing performance. The self-regulated strategy development (SRSD) model, developed by Graham and Harris (2004), is an instructional approach that aims to increase students’ active participation in the writing process, strategic awareness, and self-efficacy. Meta-analyses studies (Graham et al., 2015) reveal the strong effect of the SRSD model on written expression quality, motivation, and retention. Self-regulated writing instruction reduces pre-service teachers’ writing anxiety and improves their writing self-efficacy. Studies conducted in Türkiye (Ahıskalı & Akkaya, 2021; Müldür, 2017; Uygun, 2012) similarly reveal that self-regulation-based instruction leads to significant increases in planning, writing achievement, and retention.

Writing anxiety is defined as the negative emotion, fear of failure, and evaluation anxiety experienced by an individual during the act of writing. Pekrun’s control-value theory emphasizes that achievement-related emotions are closely associated with individuals’ self-regulation processes. Within this framework, writing anxiety can be understood as an outcome of learners’ perceived control over the writing task and the value they attribute to it. Writing anxiety is a multifaceted construct that is closely associated with several cognitive and affective factors, such as self-efficacy, motivation, and cognitive load. One of the most prominent phenomena linked to writing anxiety is writer’s block, which refers to a temporary inability to produce written text despite having the necessary knowledge and skills. Writer’s block is often considered both a consequence and a contributing factor of writing anxiety, as increased anxiety may hinder idea generation and organization. At the same time, repeated writing difficulties may further intensify anxiety levels. Studies have shown that writer’s block can emerge due to factors such as fear of evaluation, perfectionism, and lack of strategic regulation,

particularly in academic writing contexts (Zorba, 2023; Zorba & Arikan, 2025). In this respect, addressing writing anxiety requires not only affective support but also the development of self-regulation strategies that can help learners manage the writing process more effectively. Self-regulation can be considered an important factor in managing negative emotions such as writing anxiety. In the Turkish context, Karakaya and Ülper (2011) demonstrated that writing anxiety negatively affects students' writing performance and motivation.

When the literature is examined, it is evident that the variables of creative writing, self-regulation, and writing anxiety are mostly addressed independently of one another (Cremin et al., 2020; Müldür, 2017). However, writing performance requires the coordination of cognitive strategies and affective processes (Philippakos & MacArthur, 2015). Existing research on self-regulated writing instruction tends to address affective aspects such as anxiety and motivation; however, an integrated focus on creative writing and self-regulation competence has received relatively limited attention. In the Turkish context, an experimental study conducted with pre-service Turkish language teachers examined the effects of instruction based on the self-regulated strategy development model on planning and writing achievement (Ahıskalı & Akkaya, 2021). This research aims to fill this gap. By examining the effects of creative writing activities on pre-service teachers' self-regulation competencies in writing and their writing anxiety levels, this study aims to shed light on the cognitive and affective dimensions of writing education.

In the context of Turkish language education, writing instruction is a core component of developing students' language skills; however, it remains one of the most challenging areas for both learners and teachers. In Türkiye, writing instruction has traditionally been shaped by product-oriented approaches, which often limit students' opportunities for self-expression, strategic thinking, and process-based development. As a result, students frequently experience difficulties related to planning, organizing, and evaluating their writing, which may increase writing anxiety and hinder the development of self-regulation skills. These challenges are particularly critical for pre-service Turkish language teachers, as their own writing experiences and competencies directly influence their future instructional practices. Therefore, equipping pre-service teachers with both cognitive (self-regulation) and affective (anxiety management) writing competencies is essential for improving the quality of writing instruction in Turkish language education. In this respect, examining the effects of creative writing-oriented applications within this specific educational context becomes a significant and necessary research focus.

1.1. The Present Study

The present study aims to examine the effects of creative writing activities on pre-service teachers' self-regulation competencies and writing anxiety, as well as the retention of these effects over time. In addition, the study explores pre-service teachers' views on the creative writing process. In line with this purpose, the following research questions were addressed:

1. Is there a significant difference between the pre-test, post-test, and retention test scores of pre-service teachers on the self-regulation competence scale?
2. Is there a significant difference between the pre-test, post-test, and retention test scores of pre-service teachers on the writing anxiety scale?
3. Is there a significant relationship between pre-service teachers' self-regulation competencies and their writing anxiety levels?
4. What are the views of pre-service teachers regarding the creative writing process?

2. Method

2.1. Research Design

This research was designed using a mixed-methods approach. The mixed-methods research approach uses quantitative and qualitative data in complementary ways. This method aims to measure the quantitative outcomes of the research problem and to understand the reasons behind these outcomes (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018; Fraenkel et al., 2019). In the research, an explanatory sequential mixed design was used. In this design, the researcher first collects quantitative data to determine the relationships and effects among variables, and then collects qualitative data to explain the meaning, reasons, and reflections on the process of the quantitative findings (Creswell, 2014).

2.2. Study Group

The study group for this research consists of pre-service teachers enrolled in the undergraduate program in Turkish language teaching at the faculty of education of a state university. The application was conducted within the scope of the elective course, Creative Writing Education, a field education elective in the program. In the research, convenience sampling, a purposive sampling method, was used. Purposive sampling is a method that allows for in-depth examination of information-rich cases (Patton, 2015). Within this scope, the researcher had access to pre-service teachers enrolled in the course, who formed the study group. Convenience sampling was preferred as it allows the researcher to collect data naturally in the existing classroom or course environment (Creswell, 2014; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018; Patton, 2015). The pre-service teachers in the study group are in the 3rd and 4th years of the Turkish language teaching undergraduate program. There were 31 participants, all of whom volunteered for the research. The demographic characteristics of the participants are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Label	Category	n	%
Gender	Female	21	67.7
	Male	10	32.3
Class Level	3rd year	14	45.2
	4th year	17	54.8
Regular Writing	Yes	6	19.4
	No	25	80.6
	None (0)	7	22.6
Monthly Reading	1–2 books	10	32.3
	3–4 books	11	35.5
	5 or more books	3	9.7

The pre-service teachers in the study group are in the 3rd and 4th years of the Turkish Language Teaching undergraduate program. There were 31 participants, all of whom volunteered for the research. No academic achievement, gender, or age criteria were used in selecting participants. The demographic characteristics of the participants are presented in Table 1. Of the participants, 67.7% were female, and 32.3% were male, with 45.2% third-year and 54.8% fourth-year students. Only 19.4% reported engaging in regular writing, whereas 80.6% did not. Regarding reading habits, most participants reported reading 1–2 books (32.3%) or 3–4 books (35.5%) per month. This sample provides a suitable context for examining the effects of the creative writing training process in both quantitative and qualitative dimensions. The fact that participants are receiving Turkish language instruction at the undergraduate level ensures that both their writing skills and their awareness of writing

pedagogy are developed. In this respect, the study group is suitable for observing the effects of creative writing activities on pre-service teachers' writing anxiety and self-regulation.

2.3. Data Collection

In this research, data were collected using both quantitative and qualitative methods appropriate to the two stages of the explanatory sequential mixed design. Quantitative data were collected to assess pre-service teachers' levels of self-regulation competence in writing and writing anxiety; qualitative data were collected through semi-structured interviews to elucidate the underlying reasons for the quantitative findings and their perceptions of the process.

First, the Self-Regulation Competence Scale for Writing was used. It is a 25-item, 7-point Likert-type scale, adapted into Turkish by Çelikkaleli and Yıldırım (2015) based on the theoretical framework of Zimmerman and Bandura (1994), used to determine pre-service teachers' self-regulation tendencies in the planning, monitoring, self-assessment, time management, and creativity dimensions of the writing process. The possible score range from the scale is 25-175; high scores indicate stronger self-regulation competence in writing. In the adaptation study, the internal consistency coefficient was reported as Cronbach's $\alpha = .91$. In this research, the α calculated for the scale is .94, indicating that the scale is highly reliable in our sample. Secondly, the Writing Anxiety Scale, developed by Karakaya and Ülper (2011), was used. This scale is a 35-item, single-dimensional 5-point Likert-type scale. The minimum total score is 35, and the maximum total score is 175; high scores indicate higher writing anxiety. In the original study, Cronbach's α was .88, and test-retest r was .92. In this research, the Cronbach's α coefficient for the scale was .84. This value indicates that the scale has high internal consistency in the sample to which it was applied.

A semi-structured interview form developed by the researcher was used as the qualitative data tool of the research. In preparing the form, the dimensions of the Çelikkaleli and Yıldırım (2015) and Karakaya and Ülper (2011) scales were considered; questions were structured to explain why and how quantitative findings emerged. The interview form was grouped under three main themes: Self-Regulation Competence in Writing (3 questions), Writing Anxiety (3 questions), and General Views on the Process (3 questions). Three field experts evaluated the content validity of the questions, and necessary adjustments were made. Before using all research tools, the research purpose was explained to the participants, informed consent forms were obtained, and the principle of voluntariness was upheld. Field experts' opinions supported the scales' suitability for the Turkish-language teaching sample.

2.4. Data Analysis

Quantitative data analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics 25. Before starting data analysis, missing values and outliers were examined, and Z-scores and box plots were used to identify extreme values. The distribution characteristics of the data were evaluated using skewness and kurtosis coefficients, the Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests; if the values were within ± 1.5 , the distribution was considered normal. The internal consistency of the scales was assessed using Cronbach's alpha.

In the difference tests, repeated-measures ANOVA was preferred. The sphericity assumption was checked with Mauchly's test; if violated, the Greenhouse-Geisser or Huynh-Feldt correction was applied. In interpreting effect sizes, partial eta-squared (η^2_p) values were classified according to Cohen's (1988) criteria (0.01 = small, 0.06 = medium, 0.14 = large). The Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient (r) was used to assess relationships among variables. The significance level was set as $p < .05$ for all analyses, and Bonferroni

correction was applied for multiple comparisons. All analyses were conducted in line with parametric test assumptions.

In the qualitative phase of the research, data from semi-structured interviews with pre-service teachers were analyzed using thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Data analysis was conducted in six stages: familiarization with the data, coding, theme identification, theme review, theme definition, and reporting. The coding process was carried out independently by two researchers, and inter-theme agreement was assessed using the Miles and Huberman (1994) formula. When the inter-coder agreement rate was above 80%, the analysis was considered reliable. Direct quotations supported the themes, and a holistic interpretation was developed by comparing them with the quantitative findings.

To ensure the trustworthiness of the qualitative data, several strategies were employed in line with established qualitative research criteria. Credibility was supported through prolonged engagement with the data and the use of direct participant quotations. Dependability was addressed by maintaining consistency in the coding process, with two researchers coding the data independently and comparing their results. In cases of disagreement, the researchers discussed the codes until consensus was reached. Confirmability was enhanced by grounding the findings in the data and minimizing researcher bias through systematic coding procedures. Transferability was supported by providing detailed descriptions of the research context, participants, and procedures. These strategies enhanced the overall rigor and transparency of the qualitative analysis.

2.5. Creative Writing-oriented Applications

This research was planned and conducted as part of the “Creative Writing Education” course, a field education elective in the undergraduate program in Turkish Language Teaching. Attention was paid to ensure that participants had previously completed courses such as Turkish Language, Literature Knowledge and Theories, and Old, New, and Folk Literature. This ensured that students had prior knowledge of different text types and writing forms, and it provided cognitive diversity in the creative writing process. The research process includes a ten-week creative writing training program conducted in the first phase of the explanatory sequential mixed design. This program was structured to develop pre-service teachers’ self-regulation skills in writing and reduce their writing anxiety. Before the application, informed consent was obtained from participants, the principle of voluntariness was followed, and the confidentiality of personal data was ensured. During the application period, the researcher assumed both the role of course instructor and observer.

In planning the activities, domestic and foreign literature on writing education and creative writing was utilized (Bradbury, 2017; Oral, 2014; Temizkan, 2014). Each activity was designed to support pre-service teachers’ self-regulation strategies (planning, monitoring, evaluation) and creative expression skills. Students completed the given weekly writing tasks individually or in pairs, received feedback in line with a process-based writing understanding, and revised their writing. The table below shows the activities carried out during the ten-week creative writing training process, the targeted self-regulation processes, elements aimed at reducing writing anxiety, and application forms. This plan ensured that pre-service teachers conducted the writing process not only with a product-oriented approach but also with a process-oriented one, thereby developing self-regulation strategies. The activities were also designed to foster a safe, participatory, and reflective learning environment that reduces writing anxiety.

Table 2.

Activities Conducted During the Ten-Week Creative Writing Training Process

Weeks	Creative Writing Task	Targeted Self-Regulation Process	Anxiety-Reducing Element	Application Form
1	Write about the most impressive thing you saw in nature.	Planning and observation strategies	Natural environment, free theme choice	Individual writing
2	Write about a memory you spent/would like to spend with your mother on Mother's Day.	Self-awareness, emotional regulation	Sharing personal experience	Sharing-based writing
3	Imagine a fictional city and write about it in detail.	Creative planning, text pre-design	Building confidence through imagination a heroism theme with a self-efficacy feeling	Group discussions
4	You saved a life. Write about that moment.	Self-monitoring and correction	Gamification, fun task	Process-based
5	Get a coffee fortune told; write your interpretations.	Reflective thinking	Empathy-based anxiety control	Interactive sharing
6	Adopt an animal friend for yourself.	Self-assessment	Performance comfort through model safety	Paired writing
7	Rewrite the conflict types in the sample text.	Structural awareness	Attempt courage through rewriting	Text analysis
8	Change the narrator type.	Strategy adaptation skill	Anxiety reduction with visual support	Individual application
9	Narrate the human-space relationship in the short film.	Self-monitoring, multi-sensory awareness	Gamified environment, risk reduction	Multimodal writing
10	Design a digital game.	Holistic strategy transfer		Project-based work

3. Findings

This section presents the findings in line with the research questions. First, quantitative results based on pre-test, post-test, and retention-test data are reported, highlighting changes in self-regulation in writing and in writing anxiety. The repeated-measures ANOVA and correlation analyses reveal the direction and strength of these changes. Subsequently, qualitative findings from semi-structured interviews are presented to explain further and deepen the quantitative results. Overall, the findings clearly demonstrate the impact of creative writing activities on self-regulation and writing anxiety. Findings regarding the first problem statement are provided in Table 3.

Table 3.

ANOVA Results for Self-Regulation in Writing Scores

Source of Variance	Sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F	<i>p</i>	Post-Hoc	Partial η^2
Factor	38145.52	2	19072.76	41.97	.000	1–2–3	.583
Error (factor)	27267.19	60	454.45				
Within factor	4356100.54	1	4356100.54	8160.32	.000	—	.996
Within error	16020.33	30	534.01				
Total	4413433.58	93					

Post-Hoc: Bonferroni methods were used for Post-Hoc analysis; η^2 :Eta-square effect size

The sphericity assumption was not violated by Mauchly's test ($W = 0.919$; $p = .292$); therefore, sphericity-assumed values were used. A repeated-measures ANOVA shows that measurement time has a significant effect on pre-service teachers' self-regulation competence

in writing, $F(2, 60) = 41.97, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .583$. This result indicates that approximately 58% of the variance is due to measurement time, and the effect is strong. Examining descriptive statistics, it is evident that pre-service teachers' self-regulation scores are low on the pre-test ($\bar{X} = 93.10$), high on the post-test ($\bar{X} = 133.52$), and at a medium-high level on the retention test ($\bar{X} = 117.58$). As a result of Bonferroni-corrected pairwise comparisons, the pre-test—post-test difference ($\Delta = 40.42$) increased significantly ($p < .001$); the pre-test—retention test difference is also significant ($p < .001$), but a significant decrease was observed between the post-test and retention test ($p = .001$). These findings show that creative writing applications significantly improved pre-service teachers' self-regulation skills. However, there was a partial decline in these skills shortly after the process was completed. In conclusion, during the creative writing training, students' planning, monitoring, and evaluation skills were strengthened. However, upon the end of the application environment, this effect weakened somewhat. Findings regarding the second problem statement are provided in Table 4.

Table 4.

ANOVA Results of Pre-Test, Post-Test, and Retention Test Scores on the Writing Anxiety Scale

Source of Variance	Sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F	<i>p</i>	Post-Hoc	Partial η^2
Factor	12243,89	2	6121,95	159,93	.000	1–3–2	.842
Error (factor)	2296,77	60	38,28				
Within factor	1402818,11	1	1402818,11	7731,55	.000	—	.996
Within error	5443,23	30	181,44				
Total	1411802,00	93					

Post-Hoc: Bonferroni methods were used for post-hoc analysis; η^2 :Eta-square effect size

Mauchly's test indicated violation of the sphericity assumption ($W = 0.521; p < .001$); therefore, the Greenhouse-Geisser correction was applied ($\epsilon = 0.676$). Repeated measures ANOVA conducted after the correction shows that measurement time has a significant effect on pre-service teachers' writing anxiety levels, $F(2, 60) = 159.93, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .84$. This result indicates that approximately 84% of the variance is due to measurement time, and the effect is very strong.

Examining descriptive statistics, it is evident that pre-service teachers' writing anxiety scores are high on the pre-test ($\bar{X} = 137.42$), low on the post-test ($\bar{X} = 109.38$), and at a medium level on the retention test ($\bar{X} = 121.65$). As a result of Bonferroni-corrected pairwise comparisons, the pre-test—post-test difference ($\Delta = 28.03$) decreased significantly ($p < .001$); the pre-test—retention test difference is also significant ($p < .001$), but a significant increase was observed between the post-test and retention test ($p < .001$). These findings show that creative writing applications significantly reduced pre-service teachers' writing anxiety, but a partial increase in anxiety levels was observed some time after the process was completed. In conclusion, it can be said that during the creative writing training process, students' self-confidence and sense of control towards the act of writing strengthened, but when the application environment ended, this feeling weakened somewhat.

Findings regarding the third problem statement are provided in Table 5. Accordingly, examination of Table 5 reveals a moderate, negative, and statistically significant relationship between pre-service teachers' self-regulation competence in writing and their writing anxiety

($r = -.496$, $p < .01$). This result indicates that as self-regulation increases, writing anxiety decreases. Considering the coefficient of determination ($r^2 = 0.246$), it is understood that approximately 25% of the total variance in writing anxiety originates from self-regulation competence. However, this finding provides only information about the direction and strength of the relationship between variables; it does not establish a causal relationship. Accordingly, although the development of self-regulation skills during the creative writing process tends to reduce students' anxiety levels, the direction and strength of this relationship should be evaluated together with contextual factors.

Table 5.

Correlation Between Writing Anxiety and Self-Regulation Competence in Writing

	Self-Regulation	Writing Anxiety
<i>Self-Regulation</i>	1	-.496**
Sig. (2-tailed)		.005
N		31
Writing Anxiety	-.496**	1
Sig. (2-tailed)	.005	
N	31	

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Findings regarding the fourth problem statement are provided below. Data obtained from semi-structured interviews collected pre-service teachers' cognitive, affective, and self-awareness experiences regarding the creative writing process under three main themes: (1) experiences regarding the self-regulation process, (2) emotional change in writing anxiety, and (3) general views on the process.

Firstly, pre-service teachers' views regarding self-regulation competence in writing are presented in Table 6.

Table 6.

Experiences Regarding the Self-Regulation Process in Writing (Theme 1)

Subcategory	Frequency	Frequency (f)	Example statements
Gaining a pre-writing planning habit		11	I used to start writing directly; now I plan what I want to convey first. (K5)
Goal setting and determining text direction		10	When I determine what I want to convey, I don't lose the direction of the text. (K9)
Performing self-monitoring and process tracking		9	Noticing my development while writing is motivating; I can see where I get stuck. (K8)
Self-assessment and revision habit		10	I don't consider my writings finished; I review them several times. (K3)
Strategic use of feedback		8	I noticed my shortcomings with my friends' feedback; applying suggestions improved me. (K2)

The vast majority of participants reported consciously using self-regulation behaviors during the writing process. Planning, self-monitoring, and revision skills became central to the writing process; students began to see writing as a "self-managed" learning activity. In particular, strengthening goal-setting and process-tracking behaviors increased the sense of control and autonomy in text production. The effective use of feedback cycles strengthened students' self-assessment skills.

Table 7.

Emotional Change in Writing Anxiety (Theme 2)

Subcategory	Frequency (f)	Example Statement
Pre-writing anxiety and performance pressure	12	In the first weeks, having my writings read made me very uneasy; I was thinking, what if they were not liked? (K6)
Decrease in fear of evaluation	11	Now I am not afraid of making mistakes while writing; what matters is trying. (K10)
Gaining confidence with peer feedback	10	I feel more comfortable as my friends read my writings; I receive support, not criticism. (K3)
Writing is becoming an emotional relaxation tool	9	Writing relaxes me; I pour out my heart and calm down. (K4)
Increase in self-confidence during the writing process	10	As I write, my self-confidence grows; writing is no longer something to be afraid of. (K7)

The data show that students experienced high levels of anxiety at the beginning of the writing process, but as the application process progressed, this anxiety decreased systematically. Most participants stated that as writing activities progressed, anxiety gave way to self-confidence and relaxation. The writing process transformed from an “evaluation area” into an “opportunity for self-expression.” Particularly, peer feedback created a safe environment; the social comparison pressure that feeds anxiety decreased. Participants described the writing activity as a kind of emotional balancing and self-awareness practice.

Table 8.

General Views on the Process (Theme 3)

Subcategory	Frequency (f)	Example Statement
Change in perception towards writing	10	Writing is no longer just homework for me; it’s a way to express my thoughts. (K1)
Personal awareness and internal learning	9	I realized that I actually get to know myself while writing. (K4)
Continuity in writing habit	8	Even if the course ends, I don’t think I’ll stop writing. (K9)
Feeling of creativity and originality	7	Producing something of my own made me feel free. (K7)
The emotional balancing function of writing	6	When I’m demoralized, writing pulls me together. (K2)

Participants stated that the creative writing process developed not only their writing skills but also their personal awareness and inner balance. For students, the act of writing shifted from a cognitive production to a tool for self-understanding, emotion regulation, and creative expression. The evolution of the perception of writing from an “academic task” to a “personal development experience” shows that students gained internal motivation in the writing process. When the three themes are evaluated together, it becomes clear that, while students developed cognitive self-regulation skills during the writing process, they also gained in emotional control and awareness. Throughout the process, writing anxiety decreased, while autonomy and self-confidence increased. Creative writing emerged as a multidimensional learning area that strengthens not only students’ linguistic production skills but also their levels of self-awareness and psychological flexibility.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

This section discusses the findings in relation to the research questions and relevant literature. The results are interpreted with a focus on self-regulation and writing anxiety, and the relationship between these variables is examined. Based on the findings, implications for writing instruction and teacher education are presented, followed by concluding remarks.

4.1. Discussions on Self-Regulation in Writing

The findings of this research show that creative writing activities significantly improved pre-service teachers' self-regulation skills in writing while concurrently reducing their writing anxiety levels. Self-regulation-based instruction, which holistically activates the cognitive, affective, and metacognitive dimensions of the writing process, transformed the writing process for participants from merely a product creation into an active learning experience where they assumed responsibility for planning, monitoring, and evaluation throughout the process (Schunk & Greene, 2022; Zimmerman, 2000). This result aligns with research showing that self-regulation intertwines with cognitive control and emotional self-control in writing performance (Panadero, 2017). It is observed that the increase in self-regulation skills reduces the individual's writing anxiety. This relationship stems from the interaction between the individual's beliefs about their own competence and task performance, as predicted by social cognitive theory (Bandura, 2010). In the research, the systematic use of sub-processes such as pre-writing goal setting, self-monitoring during writing, and post-writing self-assessment increased individuals' sense of control over the writing process; thus, their anxiety levels decreased. Similarly, Graham and Harris (2004) emphasized that the SRSD model strengthens students' writing self-efficacy, reduces anxiety, and increases writing motivation. In this context, the findings of the current research support the indirect and regulatory effect of the self-regulation cycle on writing anxiety (Zimmerman, 2013).

The study also reveals the role of self-regulation-based instruction in improving writing quality. It is observed that individuals' strategic planning, self-reflection, and correction behaviors are determining factors in improving writing performance. Similarly, research by Uygun (2012) and Müldür (2017) found that teaching self-regulation strategies significantly improved students' written expression quality, writing self-efficacy perceptions, and attitudes towards writing. This result also aligns with the findings of Graham and Perin's (2007) large-scale meta-analysis, which found that explicit strategy instruction related to the writing process strongly predicts writing achievement. Recent meta-analyses by Graham and Harris (2018) also show that the SRSD model has lasting effects on both academic writing performance and students' self-regulatory awareness.

The integration of creative writing activities with self-regulation used in this research overlaps with the "interactive writing" approach emphasized in the literature. The progression of the writing process as a dialogue with the individual's internal discourse strengthens both self-awareness and emotional balance. Participants' association of writing tasks with their own goals throughout the process enabled them to internalize their motivation for writing. This situation is consistent with models that emphasize the reciprocal cycle among self-regulation, self-efficacy, and motivation (Harris et al., 2019; Schunk, 2014). The research findings show that self-regulation strategies function not only cognitively but also as an affective regulator in writing instruction. Participants who used self-regulation at high levels were observed to experience the writing process as an area for problem-solving and self-expression. Goal-setting, self-monitoring, and self-assessment behaviors in the writing process enabled students to develop an internal feedback mechanism for their own performance, thereby increasing productivity by reducing writing anxiety (Philippakos & MacArthur, 2015). Additionally, the self-regulated writing experience contributed to students' development of a writing-related self-identity and to their perception of writing as a personal area of achievement (Galbraith et al., 2007).

These findings highlight two fundamental effects of the self-regulation-based approach in writing instruction. Firstly, at the cognitive level, it improves text quality through strategic planning and self-assessment; secondly, at the emotional level, it strengthens a sense of control and competence, thereby reducing writing anxiety. The “writing-to-learn” framework proposed by Graham & Hebert (2010) emphasizes that writing is not only a form of expression but also an active tool for learning. The results of this study also show that creative writing, supported by self-regulation strategies, deepens cognitive learning while promoting affective improvement and motivational continuity. The research findings reveal that self-regulated instruction models are a powerful tool for raising awareness among students and pre-service teachers. Pre-service teachers developing self-regulation skills lay the groundwork for creating student-centered, strategic, and reflective writing environments in their future teaching practices. Zimmerman (2000) emphasizes that self-regulation is a fundamental indicator of an individual’s lifelong learning skills and academic self-efficacy. Therefore, self-regulation-based writing applications need to be systematically included in teacher training programs.

In conclusion, this research revealed that self-regulation-based writing instruction has both cognitive and affective effects. Providing strategic awareness, self-monitoring, and self-assessment skills in the writing process contributes to increased writing quality, motivation, and emotional well-being. In this respect, the study shows that self-regulation in writing instruction should be evaluated not only as a learning strategy but also as a “self-identity development process.” In future research, it is recommended to examine the integration of self-regulation skills into digital writing environments (e.g., online writing panels, AI-assisted self-assessment tools) and the long-term retention effects of these integrations (Graham et al., 2015; Panadero, 2017).

4.2. Discussions on Writing Anxiety

In this research, it was determined that self-regulation-based practices integrated with creative writing activities created a significant decrease in pre-service teachers’ writing anxiety levels. A decrease in participants’ fear of evaluation, failure expectations, and cognitive blocks during text production was observed; in parallel, an increase in writing self-efficacy and perceptions of task control was observed. This pattern is consistent with the current body of knowledge, which emphasizes that writing anxiety is not merely a temporary effect but a learning outcome intertwined with cognitive control, self-efficacy, and perceptions of task value (Schunk & Greene, 2022). Indeed, studies conducted on different samples in recent years consistently report that structured strategy instruction and process-oriented writing environments increase writing performance while reducing anxiety (Cheng, 2020; Hsu, 2021).

The improvement shown in our findings on the self-efficacy-anxiety axis aligns with the basic prediction of social cognitive theory: as the individual increases their sense of control and belief in competence in the writing task, threat assessment weakens, and anxiety decreases (Bandura, 2010). In this study, participants’ systematic use of goal-setting, self-monitoring, and self-assessment, supported by tools that make pre-writing planning and post-writing revision visible, shifted the focus of control from external evaluation to internal self-awareness. Particularly among pre-service teacher populations, the finding that strategic planning and genre/purpose clarity reduce uncertainty during text production and manage cognitive load has been replicated (Philippakos & MacArthur, 2015).

The control-value model (Pekrun, 2024) provides a useful framework for explaining the relationship between writing anxiety and performance. Among our participants, while anxiety

decreased, task value (the professional/academic meaning of writing) and intrinsic motivation towards achievement increased, indicating that the writing task was reframed from a “threat” to a “manageable challenge.” Current studies show that high anxiety weakens planning depth and revision quality, leading to superficial strategies; in contrast, designs providing peer feedback, self-assessment, and autonomy reduce anxiety while strengthening text organization and content development (Zhang & Hyland, 2022). Peer feedback and micro-goals can support emotional regulation during writing and encourage a revision-oriented approach to mistakes.

At the mechanistic level, the decrease in anxiety was particularly evident during the self-monitoring and self-reflection phases. Making progress visible throughout the process (checklists, draft-revision tracking sheets, self-assessment rubrics) enabled individuals to establish an internal feedback cycle, which facilitated the transition from error-avoidance-focused behaviors to learning-focused revision strategies (Panadero, 2017; Philippakos & MacArthur, 2015). Real-time feedback and collaborative writing practices may help reduce anxiety and promote participation in online writing contexts. On the other hand, at the emotional dimension, the strengthening of positive affect (enjoyment/flow) contributes to the regulation of negative affect; the reciprocal interaction between writing enjoyment and anxiety is also supported at the neurocognitive level (Dewaele et al., 2008).

The main contribution of this study lies in its integrated intervention design, which addresses writing anxiety through cognitive (planning and revision), affective (task value and self-efficacy), social (peer feedback), and instrumental (process visibility) dimensions simultaneously. This integration is particularly important for pre-service teachers, as their ability to regulate their own writing anxiety is a prerequisite for developing writing pedagogies sensitive to students' emotional needs. However, anxiety is a variable that fluctuates across contexts and time; therefore, longitudinal monitoring is necessary to assess the permanence of short-term decreases (Graham et al., 2015). Future studies could aim to match anxiety fluctuations with self-regulation indicators (self-monitoring frequency, revision depth) using time-series analyses; (ii) test anxiety regulation with emotion tracking components (instant self-report, behavioral markers) in digital writing environments; (iii) experimentally test the causal effects of peer feedback quality (focus, specificity, tone) on anxiety (Zhang & Hyland, 2022).

The present findings can also be interpreted in light of recent research highlighting the importance of structured and innovative writing practices. Previous studies have demonstrated that technology-supported and process-oriented writing instruction can enhance learners' engagement and writing performance (Grab, 2025; Rosli et al., 2025). Such approaches may also help reduce writing-related difficulties and support more effective planning and organization (Rababah, 2025). In addition, collaborative writing environments have been shown to foster interaction and improve the quality of written output (Kırmızı & Er, 2024), thereby indirectly supporting the development of self-regulation skills.

In summary, the findings of this study suggest that writing anxiety can be reduced and managed through the development of self-regulation processes, allowing it to be directed towards learning rather than suppressed. When considered alongside current literature, the metacognitive-affective integration approach in writing instruction—namely, process visibility, strategic autonomy, and safe peer feedback—is one of the strongest candidate frameworks for sustainably reducing anxiety and improving writing quality (Panadero, 2017; Schunk & Greene, 2022).

4.3. Discussions on the Relationship Between Self-Regulation and Writing Anxiety

The research results show a significant and negative relationship between pre-service teachers' self-regulation skills in writing and their writing anxiety levels. This finding reveals that as the level of self-regulation in the writing process increases, anxiety decreases; thus showing that writing performance is closely related not only to cognitive but also to affective processes. The literature consistently finds that self-regulation skills reduce writing anxiety by strengthening emotional awareness and perceptions of self-efficacy (Panadero, 2017; Schunk & Greene, 2022). Graham et al. (2015) reported that the self-regulated strategy development model significantly reduces anxiety levels while increasing students' writing self-efficacy, and that incorporating planning, self-monitoring, and self-assessment components into the teaching process strengthens this effect.

The obtained relationship pattern also overlaps with experimental and correlational research conducted at national and international levels. Self-regulation in the writing process can function as a mechanism for emotional control and motivational regulation. Learners with stronger self-regulation skills tend to experience lower levels of writing anxiety and demonstrate greater writing competence. Research conducted in the Turkish context also supports this orientation. Müldür (2017) found that self-regulation-based writing instruction led to a lasting decrease in students' anxiety levels; Ahıskalı and Akkaya (2021) reported that students who were taught planning and self-assessment strategies experienced less stress during the writing process. Self-regulation skills contribute not only to writing achievement but also to learners' emotional confidence in the writing process. This holistic evidence shows that self-regulation functions as a buffer mechanism against writing anxiety.

This relationship also takes on meaning within the framework of the interaction among self-regulation skills, emotional self-efficacy, and intrinsic motivation. Pajares (2008) states that writing anxiety is observed at higher levels in individuals with a weak sense of control; in contrast, individuals supported with self-regulation strategies transform anxiety by increasing their sense of autonomy over the task. Similarly, Han and Hyland (2022) found that peer feedback and reflective self-assessment opportunities play an anxiety-reducing, self-confidence-reinforcing role. In the Turkish context, Uygun (2012) demonstrated that the use of self-regulation strategies contributes to students' motivation to write and emotional resilience.

In conclusion, the negative correlation in this research once again underscores the need to take emotional regulation processes into account alongside cognitive control in writing instruction. In particular, the systematic teaching of self-regulation strategies to pre-service teachers strengthens writing self-confidence and academic resilience while reducing anxiety. In future research, the mediating effects of self-efficacy, task value, and emotion regulation strategies within this relationship can be examined using structural equation modeling.

These findings have important implications for writing instruction and teacher education. Integrating creative writing-oriented applications with self-regulation strategies can help create more supportive, process-oriented writing environments that address both the cognitive and affective dimensions of writing. Additionally, teacher education programs may benefit from explicitly incorporating such practices to enhance pre-service teachers' instructional competencies. Future research may examine the long-term effects of these practices across different educational contexts and explore their applicability to diverse learner groups.

Ethical Statement

Ethical permission for this study was obtained from Selçuk University's Ethical Committee on 14/10/2022, with decision number 2022/111.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

Data Availability

The data presented in this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request. For privacy reasons, the data from this study are not publicly available.

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